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Strategic Aspects of the Zangazur Transport Corridor in the Context of Sustainable Development

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Abstract: Taking into account the conditions of sustainable development in the context of modern global transformations, the strategic importance of the Zangezur Transport Corridor is examined. The strategic role of the corridor in the region and at the international level is given. The advantages of the Zangezur Transport Corridor in terms of convenient freight transportation between Europe and Asia are explained. The special role of this global transport corridor in the integration of Turkic-speaking states is noted. It is shown that the Zangezur corridor has a strong potential for creating a multifunctional international transport hub in the region. The importance of the Zangezur transport corridor in expanding international trade and mastering new markets and increasing cargo turnover is substantiated. The Zangezur corridor will have a significant impact on the cargo turnover of the countries of the region. It is predicted that trade and economic relations between Azerbaijan and Turkey will enter a new stage. The regional and global impact of the opening of the Zangezur corridor is summarized and final provisions are given.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Zangezur Transport Corridor, sustainable development, strategic aspects of the Zangezur Corridor, potential of the Zangezur Corridor.

Introduction

In the context of modern global challenges, global problems of the world economy are attracting attention. Among them, optimization of increasing costs, timely delivery of global cargoes via more profitable routes, and cargo safety are of exceptional importance. There are serious problems in the transportation of cargoes between Europe and Asia, especially in the transportation of energy resources. A number of international energy and transport routes have been disrupted due to the Ukraine-Russia war. In addition, the goals and requirements of reducing the duration of international cargo transportation require the identification of more superior and optimal routes. Azerbaijan has become the leading state in the region as the country with the largest economy in the South Caucasus. A competitive economic development model has been formed due to the stable development of the oil and gas industry. Azerbaijan is the initiator and financial donor of the largest energy and transport projects in the region. Reforms are being deepened in the country in order to ensure sustainable development (Aliyev, Babayev, Gafarli, Galandarova, Balajayeva, 2023). Azerbaijan is currently taking measures to transition to a green economy model. A number of projects are being implemented to create a green energy infrastructure. Exporting more green energy resources to European countries is one of the main goals.

In general, Azerbaijan has the status of a strategic energy security partner of the European Union. Currently, the annual amount of natural gas sent to European countries is 10 billion cubic meters, and the target is that this figure will be 20 billion cubic meters by 2027. At the same time, Azerbaijan, which has expanded its close trade and economic cooperation relations with the countries of Southeast Asia and Central Asia, performs important functions in strengthening trade relations with European countries in the near future. The work done to open the Zangezur Global Transport Corridor is a clear proof of this. It is after the opening of this corridor that the volume of international cargo transportation in the region is expected to increase several times.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The main goal of writing the article is to identify and investigate the strategic aspects of the Zangezur Transport Corridor in the context of sustainable development. For this, the benefits that the Zangezur corridor can provide to the countries of the region, as well as to the countries of the world at the international level, have been explained. The advantages of the Zangezur Transport Corridor compared to other routes have been analyzed and justified from an economic perspective. From a strategic perspective, the goal of the article is to make the countries of the world, international organizations, specialized economic and transport institutions pay more attention to the problems of opening the Zangezur Transport Corridor and to achieve the early commissioning of this global corridor.

Research Results

In modern times, the image of the independent Azerbaijani state in the region and at the international level is increasing. Currently, the processes of restoring post-conflict territories are accelerating. All this is being carried out at the expense of the Azerbaijani state's own funds. Economic reforms in the country have been intensified with the funds obtained from the export of oil and gas

resources, and infrastructure projects covering the entire territory of the country have been implemented to ensure sustainable development. In particular, large-scale projects are being implemented in the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions created in the post-conflict territories (Samadzade, 2022). On the other hand, the implementation of high-tech transport projects in the region is noteworthy. International airports have been put into operation in Fuzuli and Zangilan, and in 2026, the construction of a similar airport in Lachin will be completed (Aliyev, Melikova, 2022).

If we look at the analysis of the countries of the region, it can be noted that the opening of the Zangezur corridor will have a significant impact on the transport system and transport policy in general of each of these countries. Through this route, Iran will gain access to the Black Sea and in the future, opportunities may arise for the formation of the Persian Gulf-Black Sea corridor. Azerbaijan, Turkey and Russia will mainly benefit from this corridor and their positions will be further strengthened. With the opening of the corridor, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (Azerbaijan) will be freed from the blockade and a direct land connection will be established between Turkey and Azerbaijan. As a result, bilateral relations between these two brotherly countries will further develop. At the same time, Turkey will gain direct access to the Turkic states in Central Asia. At the same time, Russia will be able to establish a direct land connection with Armenia (The impact of the opening of the Zangezur corridor on regional transport and communication lines, 2021).

The Zangezur corridor will have a significant impact on the development of post-conflict territories. Thus, two new economic regions have been created in the territories liberated from occupation according to the new model of economic regionalization. That is, the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions have been formed and the number of economic regions in Azerbaijan has been increased from 12 to 14 (ГАСЫМЛЫ, 2022). The efficient use of resources of the newly created economic regions, the construction of modern facilities in these areas, the construction of residential areas, the formation of recreational areas, the organization of areas containing utility services, and the formation of conditions that can generally ensure normal living require continuous work, a significant expenditure of funds and labor (Алиев, 2022). In addition, the first noticeable large-scale projects in the liberated territories were related to transport projects. These projects will allow creating a large and internationally significant transport and logistics hub in the region, with access to the Zangezur corridor in the future.

In total, 44 highway projects have been implemented in the post-conflict areas. 45 tunnels, 447 bridges and 16 overpasses have been built in the region. The Horadiz-Aghband railway is being built rapidly and will allow for the formation of one of the important routes of the Zangezur Transport Corridor in the future. The Barda-Aghdam Railway will also be put into operation soon. The construction of the Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha Victory Road - a victory road consisting of very modern engineering structures, as well as the implementation of several road projects connecting the Kalbajar and Lachin regions with other liberated territories, the construction of tunnels in areas with complex relief, and the construction of new roads will ultimately allow for the acceleration of integrative processes in the region and the creation of a network of enterprises.

In addition, the Zangezur transport corridor will currently perform important functions in terms of opening up transport-logistics and communications at the international level, integrating countries, regions, continents, and intensifying international trade processes (Chedia, 2024). Along with this,

favorable conditions will be formed for accelerating the flow of goods along the Europe-Asia and vice versa Asia-Europe International Transport Route and raising trade and economic relations between continents to a new stage. On the other hand, the positive aspects of the role of the Zangezur global transport corridor in terms of optimizing costs are attracting the attention of participants in international trade channels (Gulahmadov & Huseyn, 2023).

In addition, it should be noted that the opening of the Zangezur transport corridor is also in the interest of major powers. For example, the countries of the European Union are showing great interest in the opening of this global transport-logistics corridor. Currently, as one of the countries with the largest economies in the world, the Chinese state and global Chinese companies are already expressing their intentions regarding the future exploitation of this corridor. The above arguments show the relevance and strategic importance of the Zangezur transport corridor (Mammadova, 2024). At the same time, as a result of the interruption of land connections between the Turkic-speaking states, the existing problems in the integration of these states and ensuring their geographical connectivity will be eliminated. Therefore, the opening of the Zangezur corridor is of considerable strategic importance for the Turkic-speaking states and for their economic integration (Donmez & Rehimov, 2021). We believe that the development of trade and economic relations of the Turkic-speaking states will reach a new stage and measures are already being taken in these directions. In particular, as a result of the joint initiatives of Azerbaijan and Turkey, many integration projects have been launched by the Central Asian Turkic states (Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan). It is interesting that within the framework of COP29, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan agreed on a project for the production and export of green energy to European markets.

It should be noted that the total market of the Turkic-speaking states is currently estimated at \$1.2 trillion, and this includes the Turkish economy, which is among the top 15 economies in the world, the Kazakh economy, which has a fairly strong economy in Central Asia, as well as the economies of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Azerbaijan. In general, the territories of the Turkic-speaking states have sufficient resources, natural reserves, underground and surface wealth. Nature has endowed the Turkic states with sufficient resources. There are oil and gas fields in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan. All this gives reason to say that the opening of the Zangezur global transport corridor will significantly intensify the integration of the Turkic-speaking states (Muradov, 2021).

In addition, the Zangezur corridor will create opportunities for a significant expansion of trade and economic relations between the Russian Federation and Turkey. According to forecasts, the value of cargo to be transported through the Zangezur corridor will be measured in the equivalent of billions of dollars. At the same time, if we take into account the markets of China and other Southeast Asian countries, we can expect that figure to increase significantly. Also, Azerbaijan and Russia will have the opportunity to benefit from these important commodity markets to the maximum. Thus, through the Zangezur corridor, Azerbaijan and Russia will have the opportunity to use the potential of strengthening their integrative relations with numerous world countries. At the same time, the intensity of cargo transportation between West and East, North and South will increase and international trade operations will expand.

In the near future, the prospect of opening the Zangezur Global Transport-Logistics Corridor will form new conditions at the regional and international levels. This is based on the potential to increase the efficiency of strategic cargo transportation at the international level. The Zangezur corridor is projected as a serious alternative to current international transport routes. The creation of this corridor will relatively reduce risks in the transportation of international cargo and optimize costs (Huseynov, 2021). Along with the increase in international transportation, Turkey's political power and competitiveness in the region will further increase. Thus, Turkey's economic power in the region will increase significantly, and with access to the Caspian Sea, it will gain additional opportunities to strengthen relations with other Turkic-speaking states (Sofuoglu, 2022). One of the most important issues will be the opening of a direct land route between Azerbaijan and Turkey through the Zangezur Corridor. Through this route, Turkey will gain greater economic influence compared to Iran, its historical rival for thousands of years (Dumlu & Şahin, 2024).

We believe that the opening of the Zangezur Corridor will create additional opportunities for the development of Azerbaijan as an independent state. The role of this corridor is great in terms of improving the country's economic development model and applying new economic tools. The emergence of new mechanisms can give an additional impetus to the development of the economy in general (Алиев, 2014). At the same time, the potential for creating new favorable conditions for the innovative development of the country's economy will increase. Thus, the expansion of economic relations between the countries of the region and other countries of the world will give an impetus to the intensive transfer of technologies. All this will provide additional opportunities for increasing the political and economic power of Azerbaijan as an independent state and, in particular, strengthening economic security (Алиев, 2020).

In general, in terms of accelerating and ensuring the sustainable development of Azerbaijan, it is possible to predict a multiplicative positive impact of the Zangezur Transport Corridor on all sectors of the country's economy.

Conclusions

Thus, the creation of the Zangezur transport corridor can be assessed as a historical strategic event from a regional and international point of view. We have tried to summarize its scientific and economic arguments:

- ✓ First of all, the opening of the Zangezur Corridor is in the interest not only of the Turkic-speaking states, but also of many regional and world states, including leading countries;
- ✓ The opening of the Zangezur corridor will unite the Turkish geography and strengthen the position of the Turkic-speaking states in the world economy;
- ✓ The commissioning of the Zangezur corridor will create new opportunities for the implementation of economic projects of the Turkic-speaking states and will increase the economic power of these states;
- ✓ The Zangezur corridor has the potential to form a fairly competitive international transport route between Europe and Asia, etc.

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